

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF MASS-DIMENSIONAL AND ENERGY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF SHIP BALLAST WATER TREATMENT SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The article presents an analysis of the mass-dimensional and energy characteristics of ballast water disinfection and treatment systems, focusing on ultraviolet installations and systems utilizing chlorine compounds produced through seawater electrolysis. The research findings indicate that ultraviolet systems, despite their more compact size, require twice the power to process the same volume of water compared to electrolysis units, which offer higher energy efficiency but occupy more space and have greater mass. The developed mathematical relationships between power, mass, productivity, and volume enable their use for preliminary calculations when selecting and designing ballast water treatment systems, thereby contributing to improved energy efficiency in maritime operations.

Keywords: ballast water treatment, seawater electrolysis, ultraviolet disinfection, power, mass, mass-dimensional indicators, BWTS, efficiency, treatment.

Introduction. During maritime voyages, ships engage in ballast water intake and discharge operations, which pose a risk of transferring foreign and potentially pathogenic microorganisms to new regions. This issue has gained international significance due to the real threats it poses to ecosystems and human health. The International Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast Water and Sediments [1] regulates these risks at the legislative level by establishing clear requirements for shipping. Specifically, from September 8, 2017, new vessels are required to comply with the D2 standard, and all existing ships must adhere to this standard by September 8, 2024 [1]. The D2 standard defines the maximum allowable levels of viable organisms in discharged ballast water, including specific indicator microbes that are harmful to human health. Thus, by September 8, 2024, vessels engaged in international voyages must be equipped with ballast water treatment systems to mitigate negative environmental impacts and ensure the safety of maritime travel.

Problem Statement. The issue of transferring foreign organisms and pathogenic microorganisms through ballast water during intake and discharge operations on vessels is currently quite pressing. An effective solution to this problem necessitates the use of ballast water treatment systems, among which the most common are systems based on ultraviolet disinfection, disinfection with chlorine compounds produced through seawater electrolysis, and systems that utilize chemical additives—chlorine compounds [2, 3]. Among these methods, reagent-based disinfection systems can have the most significant negative impact on the marine environment due to the introduction of toxic substances into the water. In contrast, the electrolysis method creates disinfecting compounds directly from seawater, which are then returned to the environment, while ultraviolet disinfection is the most environmentally friendly option, as it leaves no harmful residues.

When selecting ballast water treatment systems and assessing their effectiveness, it is crucial to consider technical parameters, particularly power and mass-dimensional characteristics, which influence the efficiency and suitability of specific systems. This necessitates a comprehensive analysis and comparison of the energy and mass-dimensional indicators of ballast water treatment systems to determine the optimal approach for their application.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications.

An analysis of scientific research and publications indicates significant attention has been devoted to ballast water treatment issues across various countries [2–9]. Notably, a study by the American Bureau of Shipping [2] presents an overview of existing ballast water treatment methods and their characteristics. Research [3] investigates the efficacy of disinfectant reagents on pathogenic inclusions in ballast water, while study [4] analyzes the relationship between the type of treatment system and the deadweight indicators and purpose of vessels.

Additionally, a considerable number of works focus on the techno-economic analysis of different ballast water treatment system models [4, 5] and the assessment of their productivity's impact on energy indicators [6, 7]. However, a comprehensive comparison of the mass-dimensional and energy characteristics of ultraviolet disinfection systems with those using chlorine compounds produced through electrolysis remains insufficiently researched. This limitation is attributed to the complexity of conducting theoretical evaluations, the scarcity of statistical data in the initial stages of system implementation, and the limited number of manufacturers developing systems utilizing various disinfection methods.

The objective of this article is to analyze the mass-dimensional and energy characteristics of ballast water disinfection and treatment systems, specifically

those employing ultraviolet disinfection and those using chlorine compounds obtained through seawater electrolysis. Based on statistical data regarding the energy indicators of existing ballast water treatment systems, functional dependencies have been established to facilitate the optimization of the appropriate disinfection technology selection. This will not only enable a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of different systems but also provide a preliminary assessment of mass-dimensional requirements for implementing ultraviolet disinfection during the modernization of existing systems or the development of new ones.

Presentation of Main Material. The analysis of the mass-dimensional and energy characteristics of ballast water disinfection and treatment systems, particularly those employing ultraviolet disinfection and chlorine compound disinfection obtained through seawater electrolysis, was based on examining the designs and technical specifications of existing ballast water treatment models developed by companies that simultaneously produce systems with ultraviolet disinfection and those utilizing chlorine compounds from electrolysis. This approach allowed for reducing potential parameter fluctuations due to varying technological and scientific capabilities among firms, leading to a more statistically accurate comparison.

The study focused on the ballast water treatment systems of Hyundai Heavy Industries -models EcoBallast [8] and HiBallast [8] - as well as Wartsila's models Aquarius UV [9] and Aquarius EC/ECX [10]. The EcoBallast and Aquarius UV models employ the ultraviolet treatment method, while the HiBallast and Aquarius

EC/ECX models utilize chlorine compounds obtained through electrolysis.

It should be noted that uncertainties exist in the data presented in company brochures and presentations. For example, Hyundai Heavy Industries' brochures from 2018 indicated total power for the HiBallast models, while the 2020 brochure specified only the electrolysis unit power. Additionally, there were significant changes (by 2-3 times) in the mass of some HiBallast models in the 2020 brochures, with only slight variations in occupied volume. In Wartsila's brochures, the total occupied volume and weight for the Aquarius EC/ECX models did not match the sum of the volume and weight of the equipment's components; some model weights differed by a factor of six. For this analysis, the values of the summed volume and weight of the component elements were taken as the reference data, as they were closer to the corresponding values of the HiBallast models.

The results obtained from processing the statistical data on the power and productivity of ballast water treatment systems are illustrated in pic 1.

Pic 1 illustrates a direct proportional relationship between the power and productivity of ballast water treatment systems. For ultraviolet disinfection systems, approximately 10 kW of power is required for every 100 m³/h of ballast water treated, whereas systems utilizing chlorine compounds generated through seawater electrolysis require about 5 kW for the same volume of ballast water. This indicates a significant energy savings in electrolysis systems.

Pic. 1. Relationship Between Power and Productivity of Ballast Water Treatment Systems

For ultraviolet disinfection, the trend line can be described by the following equation:

$$N_{UV} = 0,0981 \cdot Q_{bn} \quad (1)$$

where: N_{UV} - power of the ultraviolet disinfection system (kW);

Q_{bn} - nominal ballast water flow rate (m³/h).

This equation reflects the energy consumption characteristics of chlorine disinfection systems, indicating their lower power requirements compared to ultraviolet disinfection systems for the same flow rate of

treated ballast water. The obtained relationship correlates with the findings in previous studies, particularly in references [2, 5, 6].

The trend line for disinfection systems using chlorine compounds generated through electrolysis can be described by the following equation:

$$N_{EC} = 0,0517 \cdot Q_{bn} \quad (2)$$

where N_{EC} - power of the electrolysis disinfection system, (kW).

The dependencies (1) and (2) can be used for preliminary assessments of the energy consumption of ballast water treatment systems during ship retrofitting or new design projects. They can also facilitate the analysis of their energy efficiency by comparing actual performance metrics with calculated values.

Additionally, within the framework of the study, an analysis of statistical data on the mass and volume characteristics of ballast water treatment systems was conducted. The processed results regarding the mass metrics of ballast water treatment systems are presented in pic 2.

Pic. 2. Influence of the Performance of Ballast Water Treatment Systems on Their Weight

The analysis of the data presented in Figure 2 shows that the relationship between the weight of ballast water treatment systems and their productivity can be described by a linear dependence. Notably, for productivity values up to 1000 m³/h, the weight of ultraviolet treatment systems is less than that of systems using electrolytic processes. Therefore, for lower productivity levels, ultraviolet treatment is more effective in terms of weight characteristics.

ultraviolet treatment and those utilizing electrolytic processes can be described by the following equations:

$$m_{UV} = 601,64 + 2,87 \cdot Q_{bn}, \quad (3)$$

where m_{UV} - mass of the ultraviolet treatment system (kg).

$$m_{EC} = 2101,95 + 1,35 \cdot Q_{bn}, \quad (4)$$

where m_{EC} - mass of the electrolytic treatment system (kg).

The trend lines for the mass dependence on the productivity of ballast water treatment systems using

The results of the analysis of the total footprint are presented in Pic. 3.

Pic. 3. The impact of ballast water treatment system productivity on its total footprint

The total footprint of ballast water treatment systems increases according to a quadratic relationship with increasing ballast flow, as shown in Fig. 3. For systems with ultraviolet disinfection, the dependence takes the following form:

$$V_{UV} = -0,000000309 \cdot Q_{bn}^2 + 0,00266 \cdot Q_{bn} + 1,03, (5)$$

where V_{UV} – total footprint of the ultraviolet disinfection system (m³).

The total footprint of ballast water treatment systems utilizing ultraviolet disinfection is significantly smaller (approximately four times less) than that of systems employing electrolysis. This is due to the fact that

electrolysis systems require larger electrolyzers, mixing chambers, neutralizers, and additional tanks. Chlorine compounds generated during electrolysis must have time to contact the water to ensure effective disinfection, which substantially increases the total footprint of electrolysis-based systems. These systems also demand more energy to break down saltwater, resulting in a more complex design and larger dimensions compared to compact ultraviolet systems.

For systems utilizing electrolysis, the relationship between total footprint and productivity can be expressed as follows:

$$V_{EC} = 0,000000298 \cdot Q_{bn}^2 + 0,000764 \cdot Q_{bn} + 17,4, (6)$$

where V_{EC} – total footprint of the electrolytic treatment system (m^3).

The obtained dependencies (3-6) can also be used for the preliminary assessment of the necessary dimensional characteristics and the evaluation of the effectiveness of ballast water treatment systems utilizing ultraviolet disinfection or electrolysis, including general assessments of the vessel's efficiency [11].

Conclusions. Based on the conducted study, it was established that ultraviolet ballast water treatment systems, although they have more compact dimensions (approximately four times smaller), require nearly twice the electrical power per unit volume of treated water (10 kW per 100 m^3/h) compared to systems that use chlorine compounds generated through the electrolysis of seawater. Electrolysis systems, while having somewhat larger dimensional characteristics, provide energy efficiency, consuming only 5 kW for every 100 m^3/h of ballast flow. The dependencies between power, mass, productivity, and total footprint for each type of system, obtained during the study, can serve as a practical tool for the preliminary calculation of energy consumption and dimensional characteristics when designing new ballast water treatment systems or modernizing existing ones. This allows for a reasoned choice of ballast water treatment systems, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of their effectiveness and compliance with the requirements of maritime operations, taking into account various disinfection technologies.

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